

A Framework for Forward and Inverse Scattering Analysis of Finite-Aperture Metasurfaces

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Abstract—A framework for evaluating the electromagnetic field scattered from finite-aperture reconfigurable holographic metasurfaces (RHM) is presented. Based on physical optics and its Fourier representation, the framework accurately captures edge diffraction effects and obliquity in both the near and far field. It can be used either in a forward manner, to predict the scattered field for a known RHM configuration, or in an inverse manner, to predict the RHM configuration required to produce a prescribed scattering. Numerical results validate the model and highlight its relevance to forward and inverse scattering.

Index Terms—Holography, metasurface, reconfigurable holographic metasurface (RHM), scattering

I. INTRODUCTION

Metasurfaces (MS) are ultrathin structures composed of periodic subwavelength particles that enable tailored control of electromagnetic (EM) wave scattering through unit-cell engineering or dynamic reconfigurability, thus serving a multitude of potential applications [1]–[3]. Accurate modeling of near field scattering from finite aperture reconfigurable holographic metasurfaces (FA-RHM) remains challenging due to diffraction. In this work, we propose a computationally efficient framework that captures these effects. Moreover, owing to its Fourier transform (FT) based formulation, this framework admits an inversion, enabling its use as a fundamental block for phase-retrieval and holographic synthesis techniques, without relying on computationally expensive optimization algorithms [4] or limited applicability ray tracing.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The proposed calculation is based on Fresnel–Kirchhoff diffraction (FKD), which is a rigorous framework for modeling near and far field scattering from finite-aperture lenses [5]. Using Babinet’s principle, image theory, and aperture sampling, the scattered field reflected from a free-standing FA-RHM can be computed from the field diffracted from an equivalent lens embedded in an opaque screen. For clarity, the present formulation is scalar and mutual coupling between adjacent

unit cells is neglected; these assumptions are valid for linearly polarized incident waves and for RHM unit cells with minimal inter-cell coupling and broad reflection phase coverage. The formulation can be extended to vector fields (dual polarization) and can account for cell coupling through homogenization. The estimated scattered field is given by [6],

$$E_{\text{scat}}(\vec{r}_p) \approx \frac{1}{j\lambda} \iint_{\vec{r}_{\text{MS}}} \Gamma E_{\text{inc}} \Psi \frac{e^{jkr}}{r} dx dy, \quad (1)$$

where k is the wave number, $\vec{r}_{\text{MS}} = (x, y, 0)$ and \vec{r}_p are the position vectors of each MS cell and point of the projection plane (PP) parallel to the MS, respectively. $r = |\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_{\text{MS}}|$, Γ is the reflection coefficient profile of the MS, E_{inc} is the incident field “right before” its interaction with the MS, and $\Psi = 0.5(\cos \theta_{\text{inc}} + \cos \theta_{\text{scat}})$ is an obliquity factor; in the latter, θ_{inc} is the angle associated with incident wavefront direction at \vec{r}_{MS} and θ_{scat} is the angle between the MS normal and the vector $\vec{r}_p - \vec{r}_{\text{MS}}$ pointing from each cell to a point in the PP. Γ , E_{inc} and Ψ are defined on the MS aperture, i.e., at \vec{r}_{MS} .

Sampling at the unit cell centers, the integral in (1) can be approximated by a discrete double summation. Assuming the Fresnel approximation [5] holds, the scattered field can be expressed by the FT-comprising formula

$$E_{\text{scat}}(\vec{r}_p) \approx A(\vec{r}_p) \mathcal{F}\{\Gamma E_{\text{inc}} \Psi e^{j\frac{k}{2z_p}(x^2+y^2)}\} |_{(f_x, f_y)}, \quad (2)$$

where $A(\vec{r}_p) = \frac{1}{j\lambda z_p} e^{jkz_p + \frac{j k}{2z_p}(x_p^2 + y_p^2)}$, $f_x = \frac{x_p}{\lambda z_p}$, $f_y = \frac{y_p}{\lambda z_p}$ are spatial frequency coordinates. This approach is valid for the PP points that satisfy the Fresnel approximation, i.e. when $\frac{\pi}{4\lambda z_p^3}((x - x_p)^2 + (y - y_p)^2)^2 < 0.1$ for all points in the MS aperture, ensuring negligible higher-order phase terms contribution in (1) [5].

Under the Fresnel approximation, for MS apertures larger than several wavelengths, and for moderate angles of incidence, the distance-dependent terms in (2) vary slowly across the MS aperture and can be approximated by a slowly varying envelope, primarily affecting the amplitude with minimal phase distortion, thus, the FT invertibility can be exploited for phase retrieval in the inverse scattering problem as

$$E_{\text{rec}} \approx \hat{A}(\vec{r}_{\text{MS}}) A_v \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{e^{-jkz_p - \frac{j k}{2z_p}(x_p^2 + y_p^2)} E_{\text{scat}}\} |_{(x, y)}, \quad (3)$$

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where $\hat{A}(\vec{r}_{\text{MS}}) = j\lambda z_p e^{-\frac{jk}{2z_p}(x^2+y^2)}$, $E_{\text{rec}} = \Gamma E_{\text{inc}}$, and $A_v(\vec{r}_{\text{MS}}) = \langle \Psi \rangle_{(x_p, y_p)}$ is the obliquity factor spatially averaged over the PP which, under the Fresnel approximation, varies slowly when computed across the unit cells.

Finally, it should be stated that, for sampled MS apertures, continuous FT becomes discrete and can be implemented via FFT, provided that PP is sampled consistently in accordance with the MS.

III. NUMERICAL EVALUATIONS

To showcase the wavefront-shaping capabilities of the RHM, in this work, it is configured to ‘transform’ the plane wave into a vortex beam with orbital angular momentum (OAM) order $\ell = +3$. We set the MS-PP distance at $z_p = 1$ m (20λ at 6 GHz). We adopt the varactor-loaded 2×2 -patch unit cell configuration shown in the right of Fig. 1(a) with geometric dimensions given in the caption. This unit cell has weak inter-cell coupling, Fig. 1(b), and its phase can be tuned in a range approaching 270° by changing the varactor values in range 0.5-6 pF, Fig. 1(c), to enable holographic functionalities.

The FA-RHM panel consists of 60×60 cells ($0.75 \text{ m} \times 0.75 \text{ m}$). Fig. 2 (a) and (b) show the scattered field computed using (1) and (2), i.e., the full FKD and the FT-enabled approximation, respectively. The scattered fields between the FKD and FT computations are almost identical, denoting good agreement between the two formulations; minor diffraction detail errors are observed in the FT-based results, where the Fresnel approximation is not strictly satisfied far from the ‘optical-axis’, i.e., on the borders of the displayed part of the PP. The similarity between the FKD and FT scattered E-fields can be quantified by complex overlap-integrals [8]; in this case the similarity amounts to 93% which is satisfactory. Fig. 2(c) shows the assigned FA-RHM configuration which is theoretically computed to perform the plane wave to $\ell = +3$ vortex transformation functionality. Finally, Fig. 2(d) presents the reconstructed phase profile $\angle\Gamma$, i.e., the configuration of the FA-RHM, computed by inverse scattering, more specifically, solving (2) with an inverse FT for the Γ , when the FKD field E_{scat} at the PP is known. Measuring the phase difference $\Delta\phi$ between the theoretically calculated and retrieved phase

Fig. 1. (a) Unit cell and physical optics geometry, showing the incident and scattered wavefronts (WF); unit cell parameters are $2D = 12$ mm, $g \approx 0.1$ mm, $w_p = D - g$, $\epsilon_r = 2.2$, $\tan \delta = 0.0009$ and $h \approx 1$ mm. CST [7] simulation results showing (b) the magnitude of coupling between adjacent cells and (c) the tuning of reflection phase by varying the lumped varactor capacitance; $|\Gamma|$ is higher than -2.3 dB throughout this range.

Fig. 2. Scattered field calculated using (a) Eq. (1) and (b) Eq. (2), when the projection plane is at $z_p = 20\lambda$ and the same initial FA-RHM configuration $\angle\Gamma$ is used. (c) Initial theoretically calculated and (d) reconstructed $\angle\Gamma$, by inverse scattering using the FKD-predicted E_{scat} of panel (a) and Eq. (3).

distribution, we found the mean and standard deviation to be 3° and 16° respectively. The good agreement between the phase distributions and similarity of the scatter fields highlights the relevance of this framework.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presented a physical optics-based framework for modeling EM scattering from FA-RHM, enabling accurate near and far field estimation. By exploiting the FT formulation, an inverse procedure for phase distribution estimation was also demonstrated, highlighting the framework’s potential as a useful tool for holographic MS synthesis.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. L. Holloway *et al.*, “An overview of the theory and applications of metasurfaces: The two-dimensional equivalents of metamaterials,” *IEEE Antennas Propag. Mag.*, vol. 54, no. 2, p. 10–35, Apr. 2012.
- [2] Y. Liu *et al.*, “Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces: Principles and opportunities,” *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 23, no. 3, p. 1546–1577, 2021.
- [3] M. V. Katwe *et al.*, “An overview of intelligent meta-surfaces for 6G and beyond: Opportunities, trends, and challenges,” *IEEE Commun. Stand. Mag.*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 62–69, Dec. 2024.
- [4] N. Mézières and L. Le Coq, “Improvement of the Gerchberg–Saxton algorithm convergence in phaseless antenna measurements via spherical-wave filtering,” *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 71, no. 5, p. 4540–4545, May 2023.
- [5] J. W. Goodman, *Introduction to Fourier Optics*, 2nd ed. McGraw Hill Higher Education, 1996.
- [6] A. Pitolakis *et al.*, “On the mobility effect in UAV-mounted absorbing metasurfaces: A theoretical and experimental study,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, p. 79777–79792, 2023.
- [7] Dassault Systèmes, *CST Microwave Studio*, 2026.
- [8] B. E. A. Saleh and M. C. Teich, *Fundamentals of Photonics*, 2nd ed. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-Interscience, 2007.